

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE DEGREES OF VARICOCELE AND THEIR CLINICAL SYMPTOMS

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ABSTRACT

Varicocele is an enlargement of the spermatic vein network, which is one of the most common reproductive pathologies in men. Studies have shown that the relationship between the degree of varicocele and clinical symptoms can be expressed in different degrees. The disease may be asymptomatic in the early stages, and later cause pain, testicular shrinkage, and infertility. Therefore, it is important to study the degrees of varicocele and their clinical manifestations.

Introduction

Varicocele is an enlargement of the spermatic vein network, which is one of the most common reproductive pathologies in men. Studies have shown that the relationship between the degree of varicocele and clinical symptoms can be expressed in different degrees. The disease may be asymptomatic in the early stages, and later cause pain, testicular shrinkage, and infertility. Therefore, it is important to study the degrees of varicocele and their clinical manifestations.

Objectives

To determine the degree of varicocele by clinical examination. To determine the clinical symptoms of each degree. To analyze the relationship between the degree of varicocele and clinical symptoms.

Materials and methods

Type of study: observational, cross-sectional study. Area and participants: 120 men aged 18–35 years, seen in the urology department. Diagnostics: physical examination, Valsalva maneuver, Doppler ultrasound. Varicocele grades: Grade 1: Detectable only by Valsalva maneuver. Grade 2: Invisible at rest but palpable. Grade 3: Visible at rest and easily palpable

Clinical signs: testicular pain, testicular shrinkage, infertility complaints. Statistical analysis: SPSS software, chi-square test, percentage and mean values.

Results and discussion

The results show that testicular pain, testicular shrinkage, and infertility complaints increase significantly with increasing varicocele grade. Grade 1 varicocele is usually

asymptomatic and is only detected on examination. Patients with grade 2 and 3 varicocele have more clinical symptoms, which is consistent with the results of other studies. Limitations of the study: the number of men in the sample is relatively small, and personal dietary and lifestyle factors were not taken into account.

Conclusion

There is a correlation between the degree of varicocele and clinical symptoms. The higher the degree, the greater the risk of symptoms and infertility. It is important to monitor patients with grade 1 varicocele, as it can cause pain and reproductive problems later on..

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